

EMPIRICAL STUDY OF CUSTOMER SATISFATION AND LOYALTY TRAVEL E-COMMERCE IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

The development of the travel agent industry business in Indonesia is increasingly favored by the public. As time goes by, Travel Agents have entered the world of online business. Seeing the increasingly competitive competition for mobile applications providing flight tickets and online hotel bookings with an increasing number of internet users such as mobile applications, an effective marketing strategy is needed to ensure customer satisfaction and loyalty. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of product quality, price, and promotion on customer satisfaction and loyalty. The results of this study state that simultaneously product quality, price, promotion affect consumer satisfaction and loyalty, partially product quality, price, affect consumer satisfaction but promotion has no effect on consumer satisfaction. Meanwhile, product quality, promotions have an effect on loyalty, although price has no effect on consumer loyalty. While satisfaction has an effect on consumer loyalty. Even though the results are good, it can still be improved by providing guarantees for the products sold, bundling programs, and discount programs at certain times, long-term ticket booking programs, vacation package programs, and sponsorship programs in collaboration with the media both above the line and below the line. Line, membership program so that customer satisfaction and loyalty will continue to be created.

Keywords: Travel E-Commerce, Satisfaction, Loyalty.

INTRODUCTION

E-commerce includes all business activities, operations, and transaction processing that are conducted electronically. With the development of electronic commerce on the Internet, companies have changed the way they connect and deal with their customers and partners. Businesses can now overcome space and time barriers and are able to serve customers online (Changchien et.al, 2004). The Internet has supported the growth of collaborative platforms where marketers and consumers interact to develop more attractive products and services (Casalo et.al, 2010). The global outbreak of COVID has resulted in encouraging consumers to do more e-shopping (Goel et.al, 2022). Online shopping or internet shopping is increasing day by day. With the advancement of modern technology, the online market is growing rapidly. People nowadays prefer online shopping because it saves time, effort and money (Moon, 2021).

The development of the travel agent industry business in Indonesia is increasingly favored by the public. As time goes by, Travel Agents have entered the world of online business in selling tickets. In 2018 the tourism sector had interesting developments, especially in the Online Travel Agent (OTA) industry which has increased and beat other e-commerce services such as Tokopedia, Lazada and others, as reported by dailysocial.id, sales of airline tickets and hotels, rental places. Temporary stays and tickets to events became popular and became the most popular. In Indonesia, there are many websites and applications that provide ticket sales services, including Traveloka, pegipegi.com, tiket.com and others. The sales service is a company that provides a mobile application form and is the top search on Google that provides

flight ticket reservations and online hotel bookings in the form of a mobile application. The transaction process and payment system are carried out online, after making a payment, the booking code will be immediately sent via the application itself via email and sms to the user's account. Seeing the increasingly competitive competition for mobile applications providing flight tickets and online hotel bookings with an increasing number of internet users such as mobile applications, the right combination of attributes and product levels according to consumer preferences is an important thing that service companies must pay attention to in improving services according to consumer needs. And prevent customer switching due to competition between service companies which can attract customers at any time (Wibisono & Indrawati, 2019).

Customer satisfaction has recently attracted much attention among academics and practitioners, most of the academic research on this construction focuses on consumer goods using the individual consumer as the unit of analysis (Homburg & Rudolph, 2001). Similarly, the factors that drive loyalty are of great interest to academics and practitioners because consumer loyalty is an important predictor of business success (Park et.al, 2017). Most businesses such as retail businesses implement loyalty programs to increase their customer satisfaction and prevent their customers from defecting to their competitors (Zakaria et.al, 2014).

Customer satisfaction analysis is considered in relation to Kano's theory of the relationship between product quality and customer satisfaction (Conklin et.al, 2004). While the price has a different impact on sales and customer satisfaction. In particular, price increases increase sales but harm customer satisfaction (Yang et.al, 2022). With the promotion of products based on customer purchasing patterns in the past, it has the potential to increase the success rate of promotions that have an impact on customer satisfaction (Changchien et.al, 2004). To determine online satisfaction, companies need to focus their attention on promotional activities, prices and shopper experience. On the other hand, when companies are looking to determine the e-trust of repeat buyers online, companies need to focus their attention on product, price, and promotion and buyer experience. Most importantly, the results show that between e-trust and e-satisfaction, e-satisfaction has a more significant impact on the loyalty of repeat online shoppers (Moriuchi, et.al, 2016).

This study will analyze the influence of product quality, price and promotion on consumer satisfaction and loyalty to travel e-commerce in Indonesia. Thus, the importance of this research is to understand the level of customer satisfaction and loyalty to improve the company's competitiveness later (Rahul & Majhi, 2014).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction is usually conceptualized as an emotional or cognitive response. Newer definitions of satisfaction recognize emotional responses. Emotional satisfaction is confirmed by consumer responses. Customer or patient satisfaction is one of the important indicators of

quality of care because it reflects whether the services provided meet consumer expectations or not and are consistent with their values (Oparah & Kikanme, 2006).

Kotler (2000) states that satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment that comes from the comparison between his impression of the performance (result) of a product and his expectations. Dutka (1994) there are three dimensions in measuring customer satisfaction universally, namely; (1) Attributes related to product, (2) Attributes related to service, (3) Attributes related to purchase

Loyalty

Consumer Loyalty is a very important variable. Namely variables due to the influence of brand image, service quality and customer satisfaction. Factors that affect consumer loyalty consist of several components, namely: re-purchase of the same product, purchase between product lines, referring to others, showing immunity to the pull of competitors (Haryono, N., & Octavia, R., 2020). Customer loyalty is a source of competitive advantage and an important intangible asset for any organization, different marketing strategies can be used to target different market segments to increase customer loyalty (Jiang & Zhang, 2016).

Quality of Product

Product Quality, namely the perception of product performance, dimensions of Product Quality according to Tjiptono (2009), are: Performance, Features, Reliability, Conformance, Durability, Service Ability, Aesthetics, Perceived Quality. Hwang et al. (2021) stated that customer perceived product quality, satisfaction, is the main determinant of loyalty. While Moon et al. (2021) stated that product quality plays an important role in customer satisfaction in the field of e-commerce.

Price

Price is the perception of the price policy applied by the company to the product it produces, the price dimensions according to Stanton (2006) & McCarthy (2008) are: Price Level, Price Discounts, Payment Time, Payment terms, Price affordability, Price according to ability or purchasing power, Matching price with product quality, Matching price with benefits. Jiang & Zhang (2016) stated that ticket pricing has a positive and significant effect on overall passenger satisfaction and in turn strengthens customer loyalty among leisure travelers. Meanwhile, Shen & Yahya (2021) state that price has a significant positive effect on passenger satisfaction, and as a result leads to passenger loyalty.

Promotion

Kotler (2000:281) states that promotional activities are marketing efforts that provide various short-term intensive efforts to encourage the desire to try or buy a product or service. All promotional activities aim to influence buying behavior, but the main purpose of promotion is to inform, persuade and remind. The promotion dimensions are: Advertising, Sales Promotion, Public Relations, Personal Selling, Direct marketing. Orias & Sanchez (2014) Linking loyalty and service satisfaction they receive from purchasing goods and services, point to potential challenges for businesses to increase advertising and sales promotion in the media.

METHOD

This research is a descriptive-research with validity and reliability test of the variable of product quality, price, promotion, satisfaction, and loyalty to consumers of Travel E-Commerce in Indonesia. The research was conducted in 2022, quantitative in nature, in which the interpretation of research results is based on statistical processing results using the SPSS 25 software application. The research location was determined purposively, namely in Indonesia.

The sampling technique used is the Accidental Sampling technique. According to (Sugiyono, 2011), Accidental Sampling is a technique of determining the sample according to chance, that is, anyone who coincidentally meets a researcher can be a sample, if it is felt that the person found accidentally is suitable as a data source. The respondents are consumers who transact using travel e-commerce applications in Indonesia and are willing to be respondents. The sample in this study was 230 consumers. The primary data used are measurement and direct data collection by researchers with questionnaires. Filling out the questionnaire was carried out by filling in directly by the research subject.

Data analysis in this study was carried out in several tests, namely:

1. Validity & Reliability Test

Validity test is used to measure the validity or validity of a questionnaire. A questionnaire is said to be valid if the questions on the questionnaire are able to reveal something that will be measured by the questionnaire (Ghozali 2002: 135). Reliability is a tool to measure a questionnaire which is an indicator of a variable. A questionnaire is said to be reliable or reliable if a person's answer to a question is consistent or stable from time to time (Ghozali 2002:132).

2. Hypothesis Testing (t Test, F Test & Coefficient of Determination)

The t-test is a test to determine the significance of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable individually and considers the dependent constant. The significance of this effect can be estimated by comparing the t table value with the calculated t value. If t count is greater than t table then the independent variable individually affects the dependent variable, otherwise if the t count value is smaller than the t table value then the independent variable individually does not affect the dependent variable. While the F test is used to test whether changes in the independent variable have a significant effect on the dependent variable. For testing the coefficient of determination (R²) aims to determine how much the ability of the independent variable to explain the dependent variable.

3. Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple Regression Analysis is an analytical method used to determine the accuracy of the prediction of the effect that occurs between the independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y). The formula for multiple regression is as follows:

$$Y1 = + + + b3x3 + e \dots\dots\dots\text{Formula Model 1}$$

$$Y2 = + + + b3x3 + e \dots\dots\dots\text{Formula Model 2}$$

$$Y2 = a + b1Y1 + e \dots\dots\dots\text{Formula Model 3}$$

Where:

Y1 = Satisfaction

Y2 = Loyalty

a = Constanta

b1b2b3b4 = Coefficient

X1 = Quality of Product

X2 = Price

X3 = Promotion

e = standard error

RESULT & DISCUSSION

Validity and Reliability Test

Validity test

Validity comes from the word validity which means the extent to which the accuracy and accuracy of a measuring instrument in carrying out its measuring function (Azwar, 2010: 5). The formula used is Pearson Product Moment, using computer aids (SPSS 25) the results are as follows in Table 1:

Table 1: Result of Validity Test

QUALITY OF PRODUCT		PRICE		PROMOTION		SATISFACTION		LOYALTY	
VALIDITY TEST > 0.3									
X1.1	.590**	X2.1	.641**	X3.1	.648**	Y1.1	.571**	Y2.1	.636**
X1.2	.538**	X2.2	.608**	X3.2	.531**	Y1.2	.442**	Y2.2	.571**
X1.3	.575**	X2.3	.608**	X3.3	.635**	Y1.3	.636**	Y2.3	.442**
X1.4	.651**	X2.3	.697**	X3.4	.596**			Y2.4	.636**
X1.5	.638**	X2.4	.641**	X3.5	.700**				
X1.6	.653**	X2.5	.725**						
X1.7	.727**	X2.6	.779**						
X1.8	.529**	X2.7	.586**						

From the results above, all indicators of this study above > 0.3, it can be concluded that all indicators of product quality, price, promotion, satisfaction and loyalty variables are declared valid.

Reliability Test

The decision making of the reliability of a variable is determined by comparing the value of r alpha with a value of 0.60 if r alpha > 0.60 then the variable under study is reliable. The results of the analysis of the reliability of the variables in this study can be seen in the following table in Table 2:

Table 2: Result of Reliability Test

RELIABILITY TEST > 0.6									
X1	0,908	X2	0,927	X3	0,879	Y1	0,783	Y2	0,868

Based on Table 3. Above, all variables have a large enough Cronbach Alpha coefficient, which is above 0.60 so that it can be said that all the concepts of measuring variables from the questionnaire are reliable, which means that the questionnaire used in this study is a reliable questionnaire.

B. Hypothesis Test

F Uji test

The F test is used to test whether changes in the independent variables (Product Quality and Price) have a significant effect on the dependent variable (Consumer Loyalty), F test results from SPSS calculations are as follows in Table 3:

Table 3: Result of F-Test (Model 1)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	493,823	3	164,608	96,475	.000 ^b
	Residual	385,607	226	1,706		
	Total	879,430	229			
a. Dependent Variable: SATISFACTION						
b. Predictors: (Constant), PROMOTION, PRICE, QUALITYPRODUCT						

Based on the calculation Table 3, value of sig obtained significant results 0.000 < 0.05 thus the variables of Product Quality, Price, and Promotion together have a significant influence on Consumer Satisfaction of Travel E-Commerce users.

Table 4. Result of F-Test (Model 2)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1089,568	3	363,189	130,884	.000 ^b
	Residual	627,127	226	2,775		
	Total	1716,696	229			
a. Dependent Variable: LOYALTY						
b. Predictors: (Constant), PROMOTION, PRICE, QUALITYPRODUCT						

Based on the calculation Table 4, value of sig obtained significant result $0.000 < 0.05$, thus the variables of Product Quality, Price, and Promotion together have a significant influence on Consumer Loyalty of Travel E-Commerce users.

t test

The t-test is used to test whether each independent variable has a significant and significant effect on Product Quality and Price, so that the SPSS calculation results are obtained as follows in Table 5:

Table 5: Results of t-test analysis (Model 1)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2,114	0.629		3,362	0.001
	Qualityproduct	0.196	0.037	0.466	5,337	0.000
	Price	0.100	0.038	0.261	2,644	0.009
	Promotion	0.035	0.035	0.064	1.011	0.313

a. Dependent Variable: SATISFACTION

Based on Table 5 the above calculation results can be explained the influence between the independent variables on the dependent variable as follows:

- Product Quality variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Consumer Satisfaction (Y1) Travel E-Commerce users in Indonesia, this is evidenced by a sig of $0.000 < 0.05$. With the formula for regression as follows: $Y1 = 0.629 + 0.196 + e$
- Price variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on Consumer Satisfaction (Y1) of Travel E-Commerce users in Indonesia, this is evidenced by a sig of $0.009 < 0.05$. With the formula for regression as follows: $Y1 = 0.629 + 0.038 2 + e$
- Promotion variable (X3) has no positive and significant effect on Consumer Satisfaction (Y1) of Travel E-Commerce users in Indonesia, this is evidenced by a sig of $0.313 > 0.05$. With the formula for regression as follows: $Y1 = 0.629 + 0.035 3 + e$

Table 6: Results of t-test analysis (Model 2)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.021	0.802		0.026	0.979
	Qualityproduct	0.326	0.047	0.554	6,941	0.000
	Price	0.062	0.048	0.116	1,288	0.199
	Promotion	0.149	0.044	0.194	3,355	0.001

a. Dependent Variable: LOYALTY

Based on Table 6 the above calculation results can be explained the influence between the independent variables on the dependent variable as follows:

- a. Product Quality Variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Consumer Loyalty (Y2) Travel E-Commerce users in Indonesia, this is evidenced by a sig of 0.000 <0.05. With the formula for regression as follows: $Y2 = 0.802 + 0.047 X1 + e$
- b. Price variable (X2) has no positive and significant effect on Consumer Loyalty (Y2) Travel E-Commerce users in Indonesia, this is evidenced by a sig of 0.199 > 0.05. With the formula for regression as follows: $Y2 = 0.802 + 0.048 X2 + e$
- c. Promotion variable (X3) has a positive and significant effect on Consumer Loyalty (Y2) Travel E-Commerce users in Indonesia, this is evidenced by a sig of 0.001 <0.05. With the formula for regression as follows: $Y2 = 0.802 + 0.044 X3 + e$

Table 7: Results of t-test analysis (Model 3)

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4,249	0.886		4,794	0.000
	Satisfaction	0.914	0.070	0.655	13,072	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: LOYALTY

Based on Table 7 the above calculation results can be explained the influence between the independent variables on the dependent variable as follows:

- d. Satisfaction variable (Y1) has a positive and significant effect on Consumer Loyalty (Y) of Travel E-Commerce users in Indonesia, this is evidenced by a sig of 0.000 <0.05. With the formula for regression as follows: $Y2 = 0.886 + 0.070 Y1 + e$

Coefficient of Determination

Testing the coefficient of determination (R2) aims to determine how much the ability of the independent variable to explain the dependent variable. In the SPSS output, the coefficient of determination is located in the Model Summary table and is written R Square

Table 8: Coefficient of Determination

			R Square	Adjusted R Square
MODEL 1	Quality Of Product	Satisfaction	0,635	0,630
	Price			
	Promotion			
MODEL 2	Quality Of Product	Loyalty	0,562	0,556
	Price			
	Promotion			
MODEL 3	Satisfaction	Loyalty	0,428	0,426

From Table 8 the results of data processing above, the coefficient of determination for model 1 adjusted R Square is 0.630, which means that the variables of product quality, price and promotion that affect consumer satisfaction of Travel E-Commerce users in Indonesia are 63% and the remaining 37% can be explained. By other variables not examined in this study. As for model 2 adjusted R Square of 0.556, which means that the variables of product quality, price and promotion that affect consumer loyalty of Travel E-Commerce users in Indonesia are 55.6% and the remaining 44.4% can be explained by other variables not examined. In this research. Meanwhile, for the 3 R Square model of 0.428 which means that the satisfaction variable that affects consumer loyalty of Travel E-Commerce users in Indonesia is 42.8% and the remaining 57.2% can be explained by other variables not examined in this study.

2. Discussion

a. The effect of product quality on consumer satisfaction

From the results of the t test, it is stated that the product quality variable partially has a positive effect on consumer satisfaction of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. From the regression formula obtained $Y1 = 0.629 + 0.196 X1$, meaning that if the quality of the product is increased 1 time, there will be 0.825 times consumer satisfaction. Based on these results, it can be concluded that e-commerce travel consumers in Indonesia have the satisfaction to use e-commerce travel applications in accordance with the perceived product quality. Satisfaction with product quality such as Performance, Features, Reliability, Conformance, Durability, Service Ability, Aesthetics, Perceived Quality. The results of research on the effect of product quality on consumer satisfaction of e-commerce travel in Indonesia are similar to those conducted by Sari, RK, & Hariyana, N. (2019) which states that product quality affects consumer satisfaction of e-commerce users in the Situbondo region, Indonesia. Although the results are good, the quality of the product can be improved by providing a guarantee for the products sold. This will make consumers more confident in the quality of the products sold, so that consumer satisfaction will increase.

b. The effect of product quality on consumer loyalty

From the results of the t test, it is stated that the product quality variable partially has a positive influence on consumer loyalty of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. From the regression formula obtained $Y2 = 0.802 + 0.047 X1$, meaning that if the quality of the product is increased 1 time, there will be 0.849 times consumer loyalty. The results of research on the effect of product quality on consumer satisfaction of e-commerce travel in Indonesia are similar to those conducted by Fitriyana et.al (2013) which states that product quality affects the loyalty of online shop users in Indonesia. Even though the results are good, the quality of the product can be improved by providing a bundling program for the products sold. This will make consumers continue to use the product, so that consumer loyalty will continue to be maintained.

c. The effect of price on consumer satisfaction

From the results of the t test, it is stated that the price variable partially has a positive effect on consumer satisfaction of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. From the regression formula,

it is found that $Y1 = 0.629 + 0.038 X2$, meaning that if the price offered is adjusted once, there will be 0.667 customer satisfaction. Based on these results, it can be concluded that e-commerce travel consumers in Indonesia have the satisfaction of using e-commerce travel applications according to the price offered. Satisfaction with prices such as Price Levels, Discounts, Payment Time, Payment terms, Price affordability, Prices according to ability or purchasing power. The results of research on the effect of the price offered on the satisfaction of e-commerce travel consumers in Indonesia are similar to those conducted by Linardi, R. (2019) stating that the price affects the consumer satisfaction of online shop users. Even though the results are good, the price offered can be increased by providing a discount program at certain times. This will make consumers continue to transact on e-commerce travel applications, so that consumer satisfaction will be realized.

d. The effect of price on consumer loyalty

From the test results, it is stated that the price variable partially does not have a positive effect on consumer loyalty of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. From the regression formula, it is obtained $Y2 = 0.802 + 0.047 X2$, meaning that if the price offered is adjusted 1 time, there will be an increase in consumer loyalty by 0.85 times, however, consumers do not directly transact on e-commerce applications, but still go through the service process offered, so that the price offered does not affect the loyalty of e-commerce travel users. The results of research on the price offered on the loyalty of e-commerce travel consumers in Indonesia are similar to those conducted by Budiastari, S. (2018) which states that price perception has no effect on consumer loyalty of Holcim brand cement users in Indonesia. However, this can be increased again the price offered by providing a ticket booking program with a long time so that the price can be cheap. This will make consumers plan to travel long distances using e-commerce travel applications, so that consumer loyalty will be created.

e. Effect of promotion on consumer satisfaction

From the results of the t test, it states that the promotion variable partially does not have a positive effect on consumer satisfaction of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. From the regression formula obtained $Y1 = 0.629 + 0.035 X3$, meaning that if the promotion is increased 1 time, there will be 0.664 times consumer satisfaction. However, the promotional strategy carried out by the e-commerce travel provider application has not carried out maximum promotion, so based on these results it can be concluded that e-commerce travel consumers in Indonesia do not have the satisfaction to use e-commerce travel applications according to the price offered. Satisfaction with prices such as Advertising, Sales Promotion, Public Relations, Personal Selling, Direct marketing. The results of research on promotion of e-commerce travel consumer loyalty in Indonesia are similar to those conducted by Gulla et.al (2015) which states that promotional strategies have no effect on customer satisfaction of hotel users. However, this can be increased again by promotional activities by providing vacation package programs. This will make consumers plan to travel with family or friends using e-commerce travel applications, so that customer satisfaction will continue to exist.

f. The effect of promotion on consumer loyalty

From the results of the t test, it is stated that the satisfaction variable partially has a positive effect on consumer loyalty of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. From the regression formula obtained $Y_2 = 0.802 + 0.044 X_3$, meaning that if the promotion is increased 1 time, there will be an increase in consumer loyalty by 0.846 times. The results of research on promotion of e-commerce travel consumer loyalty in Indonesia are similar to those carried out by Trisnadewi & Ekawati (2017) stated that satisfaction has a positive effect on online florist consumer loyalty in Denpasar, Indonesia. Even though the results are good, promotions can be increased again by providing sponsorship programs in collaboration with the media, both above the line and below the line. This will make consumers aware of the products offered from e-commerce travel applications, so that consumer loyalty will continue to be present.

g. The effect of satisfaction on consumer loyalty

From the results of the t test, it is stated that the promotion variable partially has a positive influence on consumer loyalty of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. From the regression formula obtained $Y_2 = 0.88 + 0.07 X_3$, meaning that if the promotion is increased 1 time, there will be a decrease in consumer loyalty by 0.95 times. The results of research on satisfaction with e-commerce travel consumer loyalty in Indonesia are similar to those conducted by Farisi, S., & Siregar, QR (2020) which states that promotional strategies affect the loyalty of online transportation users. Even though the results are good, promotions can be increased again by providing a membership program. This will make consumers always use e-commerce travel applications because they are satisfied so that consumer loyalty will continue to exist.

CONCLUSION

1. Product quality variables partially have a positive effect on consumer satisfaction of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. Although the results are good, the quality of the product can be improved by providing a guarantee for the products sold. This will make consumers more confident in the quality of the products sold, so that consumer satisfaction will increase.
2. Product quality variables partially have a positive effect on consumer loyalty of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. Even though the results are good, the quality of the product can be improved by providing a bundling program for the products sold. This will make consumers continue to use the product, so that consumer loyalty will continue to be maintained.
3. The price variable partially has a positive effect on consumer satisfaction of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. Even though the results are good, the price offered can be increased by providing a discount program at certain times. This will make consumers continue to transact on e-commerce travel applications, so that consumer satisfaction will be realized.
4. The price variable partially does not have a positive effect on consumer loyalty of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. However, this can be increased again the price offered by providing a ticket booking program with a long time so that the price can be cheap.

- This will make consumers plan to travel long distances using e-commerce travel applications, so that consumer loyalty will be created.
5. Promotional variables partially do not have a positive effect on consumer satisfaction of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. However, this can be increased again by promotional activities by providing vacation package programs. This will make consumers plan to travel with family or friends using e-commerce travel applications, so that customer satisfaction will continue to exist.
 6. Promotional variables partially have a positive effect on consumer loyalty of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. Even though the results are good, promotions can be increased again by providing a membership program. This will make consumers always use e-commerce travel applications because they are satisfied so that consumer loyalty will continue to exist.
 7. The satisfaction variable partially has a positive effect on consumer loyalty of e-commerce travel users in Indonesia. Even though the results are good, promotions can be increased again by providing sponsorship programs in collaboration with the media, both above the line and below the line. This will make consumers aware of the products offered from e-commerce travel applications, so that consumer loyalty will continue to be present.

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